

THE USE OF BAMBOO AS A SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTIVE SOLUTION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

Italo Pereira, University of Brasilia, Brazil, italophellipe17@gmail.com

Tatiana Jucá, Pontifical Catholic University of Goiás, Brazil, tatianajuca@pucgoias.edu.br

Jaime Almeida, University of Brasília, Brazil, jagal@unb.br

Vanda Zanoni, University of Brasilia, Brazil, vandazanoni@unb.br

ABSTRACT

Bamboo is a material with high mechanical strength and low specific weight, grows very fast and has a wide variety of applications, characteristics that awaken more and more sustainable use in the field of civil construction. For this, numerous studies and experiments have been developed over the years, in order to certify the mechanical and physical characteristics of this material. This work, therefore, seeks to produce a Systematic Literature Review to detect the current state of research related to the use of bamboo as a building material, searching in certified databases through StArt software. The most relevant selected studies on the subject served as a survey on the studies of the use of bamboo as a constructive system in architectural projects, showing possible technology options for construction.

KEYWORDS

Bamboo; Architecture; Sustainability; Construction System.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the world has seen the worsening environmental crisis and its harmful impacts on people's lives, and on cities. According to an article published by the United Nations (UN, 2020) the extraction and processing of natural resources, such as steel used in reinforced concrete structures, or in the case of limestone and clay, essential raw materials in cement production, and also in the case of wood extracted from native forests, represent the main cause of more than 90% of the loss biodiversity and water stress, in addition to contributing about half of global greenhouse gas emissions.

With this, research for the technological development of alternative materials and construction processes, with more sustainable approaches, gains increasing importance. With increasing investments by government agencies, or private research entities from various countries around the world, we seek alternatives of minimizing the use of non-renewable resources, energy saving in human processes and activities, and in reducing waste. Whereas the construction industry, both in construction and demolition processes, represents the most impactful human activity on the environment (PADOVAN, 2010).

The use of bamboo as a building material is a trend that becomes increasingly addressed and studied, although it is currently a little used material, with its use erroneously associated with simple and improvised constructions, as well as raw material for the production of decorative adornments and finishing details (OLIVEIRA, 2013). This material can serve as a possible substitute for wood, both used in conjunction with conventional ones, providing hybrid systems, as a base material for innovative constructions. The truth is that bamboo can contribute enormously to the reduction of deforestation of native forests, besides helping to reduce the monoculture system in force in Brazil, implementing the planting of bamboo species on an industrial scale.

In addition to the positive points already mentioned, bamboo planting still has other strengths, such as shorter growth cycle than that of wood. It also has high productivity per hectare, not to mention the low cost of planting and the ease of cultivation, which also does not require very complicated handling tools. Bamboo is also a very important species in the revitalization and recovery of degraded areas, which is a relevant theme in the current Brazilian scenario, with the monoculture system causing exhaustion of many producing areas. In addition to all this, the Brazilian climate is very conducive to plant growth, not to mention the large number of bamboo species already existing in the national territory (PADOVAN, 2010).

It is a sturdy and durable plant, and there are numerous examples of houses, bridges and furniture created with bamboo. It presents itself as a good alternative to wood, as it has faster growth. Another important point that points to bamboo as an option that should be considered, is its ability to remove carbon dioxide from the air, since the stems of the bamboo sprout and grow fast.

Therefore, it is extremely important that bamboo is more targeted and valued in research and academic studies, to discuss and reveal new ways to take advantage of the potentialities of this material as an option in the scenario of the need for change and innovation in which humanity finds itself.

OBJECTIVE

The main objective of the work is to conduct a survey of the panorama of studies on the use of bamboo as a construction system in architectural projects, investigating possible technology options in construction. In particular, it aims to produce a Systematic Literature Review to probe the current state of research related to the use of bamboo, using certified databases to obtain scientific articles.

METHOD

A Systematic Literature Review consists of a secondary, systematic, broad and reproducible study, which aims to identify, evaluate and synthesize the main relevant primary work points on a specific topic. Therefore, it is necessary to follow an explicit methodological approach in explaining the procedures that led to it, including all relevant material; and thus can be reproduced by others who seek to follow the same work approach (OKOLI, 2019).

SEARCH QUESTION AND SEARCH TERMS

The first stage of the work consists in the formulation of the research question: "what is the state of the art of research related to the use of bamboo as a constructive method in buildings?" With the research question defined, the *keywording method* was used, which consists of the selection of keywords and insertion in the databases, to find the related articles on the subject in question.

For each database, a specific *search string* was used in order to increase the scope of the searches and obtain the maximum number of jobs from each database in question. In the SciELO database, the keywords used were Bamboo AND Construction. In Science Direct, the keywords used were Bamboo AND Construction System AND Architecture. In the Scopus database the keywords adopted were "Bamboo"; "Construction"; Architecture.

SEARCH DATABASE

Three databases were used to obtain the articles, SciELO, Science Direct and Scopus. The time frame adopted to obtain the studies was from 2017 to 2021, and the types of work obtained were only research articles. It has also been defined that the *search string* terms should appear in the title, summary, or keywords of any area of Scopus/Elsevier. The searches in SciELO resulted in 11 articles, already in Science Direct, the searches resulted in 130 articles. The titles of the public scars marked in the search were 'Construction and Building Materials'; 'Materials Today: Proceedings'; 'Journal of Building

Engineering', including the thematic areas 'Engineering'; Materials Science; Earth and Planetary Sciences; and 'Environmental Science'.

In Scopus, 24 articles were obtained, with the thematic areas 'Engineering'; 'Environmental Science'; 'Materials Science', being English, Spanish and Portuguese the languages chosen for the search. Figure 1 shows the distribution of selected articles by the database.

Figure 1: Graph of the number of jobs for each database. Source: Author, 2021.

SOFTWARE START

First, within the StArt software, the 'Protocol' section was filled in, where it was necessary to insert the objective of the work, the research question, the main keywords, which in this case are: "Bamboo Architecture"; "Civil Construction"; Constructive System and Sustainable building.

After that, the field of defining the selection criteria of the articles in the sources was filled in, which consist of: "Cited in the keywords"; "Quoted in summary"; "Quoted in the title". The language of the works is also defined in the software protocol, and in this case were English, Spanish, and Portuguese. The methods of searching the sources were: "Containing the keywords used in combination in the abstract or title and has an approach that deals with the use of bamboo as material in civil constructions."

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

The inclusion criteria of the obtained studies were: "Bamboo quoted in the keywords"; "Bamboo quoted in summary"; "Bamboo quoted in the title". The exclusion criteria of the studies were: "Studies related to another area of study"; "Studies outside the period between 2017 and 2021"; "Approach that does not address the use of bamboo as a building material"; "Full text not available". The works obtained from the three databases mentioned were downloaded in RIS format and inserted in the *Software StArt (State of the Art through Systematic Review)*. This software was developed by the Software Engineering Research Laboratory (LAPES) of the Federal University of São Carlos - UFSCar.

The work resulting from the primary searches in the databases is imported into the StArt software, and thus the planning phase in the program ends, beginning the review execution process. All 165 inserted papers have moved on to the selection step. Duplicate papers were initially rejected, and therefore, a manual process of acceptance or rejection of the work was initiated, according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. It was also called a reading priority for each article, with the ratings "Very high"; "High"; "Low" and "Very low".

After the selection process, 74 articles were accepted, 90 were rejected and one paper was characterized as duplicated. Then, the extraction process begins with the reading of the titles and abstracts of the works, to determine whether the work fits the desire of the theme.

Figure 2: a) Graph of the papers accepted, rejected and duplicated in the selection phase. Source: Author, 2021

b) Graph of the papers accepted and rejected in the extraction phase. Source: Author, 2021

Of the total of 74 (Figure 2), 58 papers were accepted, with 16 papers being rejected, for having some exclusion criteria, or for not dealing with the use of bamboo as a building material.

As can be seen in Figure 3, among the 74 articles in the extraction process, the 'Very high' reading priority was stipulated for 32 papers, or 43%, 25 papers with 'High' priority, or 34%, 15 jobs with low priority, or 20% and 2 jobs with 'Very low' reading priority, or 3% of the total. These reading priority categories were made available by the *StArt program itself* in its article filtering steps.

Figure 3: Graph of the number of jobs per read priority in the extraction phase. Source: Author, 2021.

In Figure 4 it is possible to perceive the criteria met by the accepted papers, with the keywords *used in the search string present* in the keywords of the articles, or in the abstracts, or titles of the respective works. Figure 5 shows the exclusion criteria that the studies present, among them, 'Studies related to other areas of study'; 'Studies outside the period between 2017 and 2021'; 'Approach that does not treat bamboo as building material' and 'Full text not available'.

After the 58 papers have been accepted, a cross-sectional reading was initiated to score the main subjects and contributions to the desired theme, effectively initiating a systematic review of literature aimed at investigating the state of the art of studies related to the use of bamboo as a sustainable building material.

Figure 4: Graph with the inclusion criteria. Source: Author, 2021.

Figure 5: Graph with the exclusion criteria of rejected papers. Source: Author, 2021.

Finally, a *word cloud graph* was generated in StArt (Figure 6) with the main words present in the titles, with the largest words being the ones that were most cited in the accepted works, thus obtaining a more in-depth view of the main themes and subjects presented in the works about bamboo. A word cloud graph was also generated with the most influential authors, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Word cloud graph with the most quoted words in the works. Source: Author, 2021.

Figure 7: Word cloud graph with the most influential authors on the topic. Source: Author, 2021.

ANALYSIS OF THE INFORMATION COLLECTED IN THE ARTICLES

Fifty-eight published articles related to bamboo theme and technological applications in some areas of civil construction were identified. These 58 papers obtained from the filtering process were read briefly, in order to evaluate which ones added more innovative and relevant information for the theme. After reading and preliminary analysis, 10 studies were really innovative regarding the use of bamboo as a constructive system. Aiming at the delimitation of this article and its scope, only the 7 most relevant papers among the 10 were discussed here.

Table 1 presents the panorama of the 7 papers that address the use of bamboo as a sustainable constructive solution, presenting the authors, applications and main results, in chronological order, with the latest ones at the top of the board.

Authors	Application	Main Result
WASSENHOVE et al. (2021)	Propose a removable bio composite connection system printed in 3D for bamboo spatial structures.	The system has good flexibility and can be a solution for application in small temporary structures, even in Europe.
TAHMASEBINIA et al. (2021)	Make a numerical and design analysis of a grid structure of bamboo arches.	Proposed a cross bow design, with good resistance to wind action and good resistance to loads of the structure.
MAIKOL et al. (2020)	Creates and analyze geometric structures of bamboo, using the material as a means of sustainable architecture development.	The use of bamboo in civil construction is becoming more recurrent, due to its rapid assembly on the site, low transport cost, etc.
WANG et al. (2019)	Study the use of structural glued laminate bamboo in light structures, and the connections of laminated bamboo walls.	Based on the test results, a design was proposed using glued laminate bamboo.
HONG et al. (2019)	Study the various forms of connection in bamboo structures.	The author concluded that the most fragile area of a bamboo structure is the joints, so it is the field that requires more attention.
WU, Y.; XIAO, Y. (2018)	Analyze the mechanical properties of bamboo, its impact on the environment and its application in a hybrid spatial truss structure.	has succeeded in designing a hybrid space truss structure, that can support, roofs, etc.

RICHARD et al. (2017)	Test the capabilities of bamboo and its connections in order to propose a design for a school made of bamboo in the Philippines.	greater incentive for bamboo research is needed, as it has weaknesses, especially in connections, string connection was used in the design.
-----------------------	--	---

Table 1: Overview of bamboo research articles, arranged in chronological order, from the most recent to the oldest. Source: Author, 2021.

Van Wassenhove Hotels et al. (2021) proposed a connection system for bamboo stems based on connections printed on 3D machines. Bites. The print pattern was created using simplified 3D software. This structural connection to the bamboo presented in the work is made parametrically, so that the geometry of the connection can adapt to the size of the bamboo stem, as can be seen in Figure 8. The software used for this purpose was Rhinoceros 3D 6.0.

Figure 8: Detail of the 3D printed connection system. Source: van Wassenhove et al. (2021).

Such a connection system can be used in the production of temporary structures and furniture. The main conclusions of the research consider that the bio composite material printed in 3D exhibits very low dispersion both in the longitudinal direction and in the transverse direction. The combination of the parametric design process and 3D printing allows the derivation of a standardized system. For the authors, automating design and production processes has allowed to increase of the potential creativity for freeform structures, without any major decrease in process efficiency.

Further experimental results are needed to confirm the rigidity of the connection system, proving that the flexibility offered by the introduced connection system allows you to use it for structures temporary and small-scale applications, offering good opportunities for the introduction of bamboo structures in European construction.

Richard et al. (2017) initially addressed the issue of bamboo standardization, citing ISO 22156:2004 and ISO 22157:2004, which regulate and present practices and recommendations in the use of structural bamboo in architectural projects. The Colombian Building Code (NSR-10), and the National Building Code of India (BIS, 2005), among others, were also mentioned. With the earthquake and typhoon that struck the Philippines in October 2013 of magnitude 7.3, most of the islands suffered considerable damage. As part of the reconstruction process, actLAB, a collaborative architectural design group located in New York, worked to rebuild two destroyed schools in the rural towns of Maribojoc and Loon.

a) Internal rendering of the project

b) Isometric perspective of the structure

Figure 9: Project images. Source: Richard et al. (2017).

The bamboo species used in the project is *Bambusa Blumeana* (Kawayan Tinik), which is native to the Philippines. An experimental program of testing the connections was carried out in order to obtain the mechanical strength values of bamboo. Manila rope was used in traditional bamboo and truss connections. And the experimental tests conducted on bamboo and steel trusses connections helped and facilitated the formulation of structural design for the architect, local engineer and bamboo joiner. Internal images and the structural system are present in Figure 9. However, more standardized testing methods are necessary for more reliable information to be available about the mechanical properties of bamboo.

Medina Yor Maikol et al. (2020) studied projects and structures made of bamboo, on an expedition trip between 2017 and 2019, in settlements of Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico and Indonesia. The authors cite some architects such as Oscar Hidalgo López (Colombia), Simón Vélez (Colombia), Simón José Samper (Colombia), Andrés Bäßler Ramírez (Colombia / Germany), Jorge Morán Ubidia (Ecuador), Khosrow Ghavami (Iraq / Brazil), Elora Hardy (Indonesia / USA), and Richard Buckminster Fuller (USA). Based on the work of these architects mentioned above, it was possible to research and discover the use of bamboo as a structural and finishing material, in addition to new solutions for design for use in contemporary architecture.

The Sharma Springs house project (Bali, Indonesia), seen in Figure 10 (a), presents itself as one of the most interesting projects currently in the world with the use of bamboo. It consists of a house inserted in the rainforest, has six levels and a total built area of 750 m², being the tallest bamboo construction in Bali.

The Gallery project in Figure 10 (b) is made of Bamboo *Guadua spp.* and meets the requirements of being a local material, with low transport cost, quick assembly of the structure, which accelerates the construction process of the work and high recovery of the environment whereas bamboo grows very rapidly.

Figure 10: Images of the analyzed projects. Source: Medina Yor Maikol et al. (2020).

Wang et al. (2019) studied the use of Gluminated Bamboo (*GluBam*), as well as the performance of the connection systems used in the light walls of glued laminated bamboo. The production of bamboo leaf plates for use in the production of frame elements and coating panels of processed bamboo walls has been studied, as is seen in Figure 11. For the due connection of these laminated bamboo walls, it was proposed to study the metallic connections for this. Thus, experimental research was developed in the connections with three types of nails, being 1) Nails ST (T-shaped steel nails) that can be triggered by air gun, 2) common nails and 3) high strength nails.

Figure 11: Images of bamboo fiber structure and board. Source: Wang et al. (2019).

After these tests, a model wall was modeled, with a dimension of 2.4 m high and 1.2 m wide. Therefore, the experimental research of mechanical behavior in the wall connections of Glubam Laminate Bamboo (*GluBam*) aimed to generate a greater understanding of such a system and create a database for future BIM-based constructions.

Hong et al. (2019) studied the connections to original bamboo structures, first addressing the traditional connecting joints in bamboo structures, such as the fitting joints and the mooring joints, as demonstrated in figure 12. In addition to traditional connections, the authors addressed modern connections, which can be screwed connections, as shown in Figure 13.

a) Fitting joint

b) Mooring joint

Figure 12: Snap joint, and bollards. Source: Hong et al. (2019).

Figure 13: Details of screwed connections. Source: Hong et al. (2019).

It is also possible to list connections with steel members and steel plate joints, which are formed by screws, rebar hooks, steel pipes, clamps, etc. They have the characteristics of strong connection, convenient assembly and disassembly and can be applied to the connection in various ways, as shown in Figure 14. It is also possible to list the reinforced joints with filling, to ensure the stiffness and stability of the joints, fillers are added on the cavity of the bamboo and then connected by prefabricated metal screws and connectors, as shown in Figure 15. Colombian architect Simón Velez, for example, uses cement mortar to improve the performance of the bamboo connections of his works.

Figure 14: Detail of the connections of steel members. Source: Hong et al. (2019).

Figure 15: Detail of the reinforced joints with mortar filling. Source: Hong et al. (2019).

Wu and Xiao (2018) studied the production process and mechanical properties of glued laminated bamboo, for application in a hybrid spatial truss, composed of laminated bamboo and steel. *GluBam* (*Glue Laminated Bamboo*) pieces are mostly used for superior compressive stress, while steel tubes are mostly used in stress zones bottom of the structure.

The production process of the structural parts of Glue Laminated Bamboo (*GluBam*) consists of two steps, the first being the pressurization of the layers of bamboo blades, in plates under high temperature. And the second step consists of laminating the cut elements of the plates into structural elements, at room temperature, or under high temperature. The cross-section of the *GluBam* is 55.56 mm, and the steel tube has a diameter of 42 mm, and a wall thickness of 4 mm, as seen in Figure 16.

The connections of the spatial truss consist of upper fixing plates, to connect the upper *GluBam* elements, and the bottom fixing plates, which connect the steel with the lower *GluBam* elements. These plates are 6 mm thick.

The top plate is fixed by means of two steel screws in each direction, inside the laminated bamboo. The crossed oblique steel plates employed between steel pipes and bamboo elements are welded at the bottom of the cross shape, with steel plates to connect the elements of the bamboo web laminated, and are fixed with three screws on each side.

a) Details of the section of Laminated Bamboo and steel pipe b) Details of connections made by fixing plates

Figure 16: Details of structural parts. Source: Wu and Xiao (2018).

The hybrid space truss system of laminated bamboo and steel has been specially designed and built for a rain cover, for an office building. Figure 16 shows the section of the steel pipe and glued laminate bamboo, in addition to the Fixing Plates. The final structure has dimensions of 12 m long and 3.6 m wide, and the distance between the supports of 8.4 m, as seen in Figure 17.

Figure 17: View of the finished structure supporting the glass marquee. Source: Wu and Xiao (2018).

Tahmasebinia et al. (2021) discussed the proposition of a curved structure, which makes use of *Bamboo Scrimber*, which consists of industrially processed bamboo parts, seeking to create new information and parameters for future studies, and creation of designs of bamboo structures.

The process that bamboo stem goes through to become *Bamboo Scrimber* is first truncation and division, and then defibering, drying, immersion in liquid treatment, assembly, pressing, cold curing and hot curing or hot pressing.

Properties	Values
Modulus of Elasticity (E)	13,5-32,3 GPa
Poison Coefficient	0,26-0,52
Density (ρ)	720-1300 kg/m ³

Figure 18: Mechanical properties of Bamboo Scrimber. Source: Tahmasebinia et al. (2021).

Properties	Values
Tension	296,2 MPa
Compression	134,9 MPa
Inflection	119 MPa
Shear	15 MPa

Figure 19: Load resistance properties of Bamboo Scrimber. Source: Tahmasebinia et al. (2021).

Three structural designs were proposed for the project, initially, which served as the basis for the creation of a definitive final structure, improved from the previous ones, as seen in Figure 20. The three designs consist of curved bamboo elements, which were used for the formation of a grid-shaped spatial structure.

The work proposed possible design solutions to manufacture curved bamboo roof structures. Three designs were suggested and analyzed in the question of static load behavior, as seen in Figure 21. using finite element analysis through Strand7.

Figure 20: Three proposed initial design solutions. Source: Tahmasebinia et al. (2021).

The main novelty of the present study was to suggest a simple and reliable method of finite elements to design some unique structures for which there are no guidelines in practice. The three designs initially proposed used *Bamboo Scrimber*, while the new definitive design used natural bamboo, as it was found that processed bamboo tends to suffer deformation more easily than natural bamboo, which may be due to its shape and its high stiffness.

Figure 21: Bamboo structural drawing solution desirable for design. Source: Tahmasebinia et al. (2021).

CONCLUSION

By conducting the Systematic Literature Review, it was possible to investigate the panorama of studies related to the use of bamboo as a sustainable building material. And this was achieved, thanks to the use of computational tools that facilitated the search process. With the help of reliable databases, such as Scopus, Science Direct and SciELO, the works could be collected, downloaded in RIS format and later inserted in *the StArt* software. Thanks to *StArt*, numerous graphics could be created and used in this research. Several filters of the articles were made, until the most suitable and innovative ones were found for the theme. This filtering process was done through criteria established by the author himself, based on existing RSL works. Thus, of 165 studies collected from databases and inserted in the program, it was possible to specifically delimit 7 articles studied and discussed, obtaining the main points and contributions to the chosen theme.

Studies addressing the use of bamboo as a sustainable building material are numerous and make it possible to affirm that the options for the use of bamboo are very large, since its use as a structural system, in beams and columns, and elements of trusses, up to a less striking use, as in the case of walls, floors and ultimately decorative elements. It was noticed that many studies evaluated the possibilities of bamboo, through experimental trials that revealed its mechanical and physical properties. The connections in bamboo structural systems proved to be a key point, because they are complex, due to the variable size of bamboo stems, which makes it difficult to standardization of joints. It was possible to notice that there is a wide variety of connection options for different bamboo structures, both traditional connections, used by traditional builders and traditional people for some time, and modern

connections, created through laboratory tests, using for example screws and steel plates for fixing the structures.

Therefore, it is possible to conclude that bamboo is becoming increasingly a viable option in the field of civil construction, with new studies emerging based on innovative technologies both in the field of architecture and in the field of materials. For the comprehensive use of bamboo to become a more concrete reality, greater investment is needed in research and innovations that make it possible to overcome the weaknesses of the material.

REFERENCES

Hong, C., Li, H., Lorenzo, R., Wu, G., Corbi, I., Corbi, O., Xiong, Z., Yang, D., & Zhang, H. (2019). Review on connections for original bamboo structures. **Journal of Renewable Materials**, 7(8), 714–730. <https://doi.org/10.32604/jrm.2019.07647>

Medina Yor Maikol, S., Vasily Maksimovich, S., Galina Ivanovna, B., & Ainur, S. (2020). Bamboo Structures for Modern Sustainable Architecture. In **ISVS e-journal** (Vol. 7, Issue 3).

OLIVEIRA, L.F.A. de. **Knowing bamboos and their potentialities for use in civil construction**. 2013. 90f. Monograph (Specialization in Civil Construction) - School of Engineering, Federal University of Minas Gerais, Belo Horizonte, 2013.

OKOLI, C. Guide to Conducting a Systematic Literature Review. (Translated by David Wesley Amado Duarte). **EaD in focus**, v. 9, n. 1, p. 1-40, 2019.

PADOVAN, R.B. **Bamboo in Architecture: Structural Connection Design**. Master's thesis - Paulista State University. Bauru, 2010.

UN report, **Emissions from the construction sector reached record highs in 2019**, published on December 16, 2020. Accessed 14/08/2021, available at: <<https://www.unep.org/pt-br/noticias-e-reportagens/comunicado-de-imprensa/emissoes-do-setor-de-construcao-civil-atingiram>>.

Richard, M. J., Kassabian, P. E., & Schulze-Ehring, H. S. (2017). Bamboo active school: Structural design and material testing. **Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers: Structures and Buildings**, 170(4), 275–283. <https://doi.org/10.1680/jstbu.16.00070>

SOBRAL, L. et al. **Hitting target 2: Amazonian wood consumption and forest certification in the State of São Paulo**. Bethlehem: Imazon, 2002. 72p.

Tahmasebinia, F., Ma, Y., Joshua, K., Sepasgozar, S. M. E., Yu, Y., Li, J., Sepasgozar, S., & Marroquin, F. A. (2021). Sustainable architecture creating arches using a bamboo grid shell structure: Numerical analysis and design. **Sustainability (Switzerland)**, 13(5), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052598>

van Wassenhove, R., de Laet, L., & Vassilopoulos, A. P. (2021). A 3D printed bio-composite removable connection system for bamboo spatial structures. **Composite Structures**, 269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2021.114047>

Wang, R., Wei, S. Q., Li, Z., & Xiao, Y. (2019). Performance of connection system used in lightweight glulam shear wall. **Construction and Building Materials**, 206, 419–431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.02.081>

Wu, Y., & Xiao, Y. (2018). Steel and glulam hybrid space truss. **Engineering Structures**, 171, 140–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.05.086>

Yaday, M., & Mathur, A. (2021). Bamboo as a sustainable material in the construction industry: An overview. **Materials Today: Proceedings**, 43, 2872–2876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.01.125>

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.